

color of feeding materials. It is fast moving and can be seen as a small moving dot on seedlings.

We attempted mass rearing of *T. palmarum* on different diets of fungi grown on several artificial media. It multiplied vigorously on *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Alternaria padwickii*, and *Curvularia* sp. On 10 different media, the mites grew best on 4% oatmeal agar (OMA). Egg-to-egg life cycle took 10-12 d on *F. moniliforme* grown on 4% OMA. Mites produced about 247 eggs, of which 210 hatched. About 167 adults emerged from the hatched larvae. Females reproduced parthenogenetically. There was no male population in the culture. □

***T. palmarum* populations in seedlings and leaf sheaths in 1983 dry and wet season nurseries, Cuttack, India.**

Variety	Populations (adults, juveniles, and eggs) 10 seedlings ^a
Ratna	34 b
Karuna	30 ab
CR1009	28 ab
CR1014	18 ab
Jaya	25 ab
Vijaya	19 ab
Pusa 2-21	2 a
Kalinga-I	16 ab
Supriya	15 ab
Jagannath	19 ab

^aAv of 10 replications. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

T. palmarum mite, Cuttack, India.

Parasitization of yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* eggs

H. S. Kim and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

We surveyed the IRRI farm to determine the extent of parasitization of YSB egg masses. Egg masses were randomly collected at weekly intervals from Jul to Aug 1984 from rice fields, 15-20 d after transplanting, and brought to the laboratory for collection of emerging parasites.

Three species of hymenopterous parasitoids — *Tetrastichus schoenobii*, *Teleonomus rowani*, and *Trichogramma japonicum* — were reared from 455 egg masses (Table 1). *T. schoenobii* was the most abundant among the species, parasitizing 95% of the eggs. *T. schoenobii* may be

the most efficient because two to four (av of three) host eggs are needed to complete the larval period. *T. japonicum* was so small that one to four (av of two) parasites developed from one host egg. Thus, in calculating percent parasitism by *T. schoenobii*, the number of emerged parasites is multiplied by 3. For *T. japonicum*, the number of emerged parasites is divided by 2 (see footnote to Table 1). Female parasites were five times as abundant as males.

Multiparasitization occurs in YSB egg masses (Table 2). Eighty-eight percent of the egg masses were parasitized by one or a combination of parasite species. The highest parasitization (35%) was by a combination of *T. rowani* and *T. japonicum*. □

Table 2. Multiparasitization of YSB egg masses (n = 485) by 3 parasites, IRRI, Jul-Aug 1984.

Parasite combination	Parasitization of egg masses (%)
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. schoenobii</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	9.8
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	34.6
<i>T. rowani</i> + <i>T. schoenobii</i>	17.7
<i>T. schoenobii</i> + <i>T. japonicum</i>	11.5
<i>T. schoenobii</i>	9.5
<i>T. rowani</i>	3.2
<i>T. japonicum</i>	1.2
Total	87.5

Table 1. Percent parasitization of YSB egg masses and the sex ratio of the parasitoids, IRRI, Jul-Aug 1984.

Parasite	Egg masses (no.)	Eggs parasitized ^a (%)	Parasites (no./egg mass)		Stem borer larvae (no./egg mass)		Sex ratio (male:female)
			Emerged	Unemerged	Hatched	Unhatched	
<i>T. schoenobii</i>	46	94.7	18.7	2.0	1.5	2.0	5:1:1
<i>T. rowani</i>	15	45.3	20.8	10.3	18.4	19.1	5:3:1
<i>T. japonicum</i>	6	8.1	10.0	3.0	63.8	9.9	4:7:1

^aCalculated as: $T. schoenobii = \frac{(C \times 3) + (D \times 3)}{(A + D) + (C \times 3) + (D \times 3)} \times 100$

$T. rowani = \frac{C+D}{A+B+C+D} \times 100$

$T. japonicum = \frac{C/2 + D}{A + B + (C/2) + D} \times 100$

Where A = no. of hatched stem borer larvae, B = no. of unhatched stem borer larvae, C = no. of emerged parasites, and D = no. of unemerged parasites.

A simple technique of rearing yellow stem borer (YSB) *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker)

F. G. Medrano and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

Insecticide evaluation and host plant resistance studies using YSB have been limited by an inadequate insect supply during certain months. Previous workers made unsatisfactory mass rearing attempts by placing larvae on 40- to 45-d-old rice plants or cut stem pieces of flowering plants, or feeding them artificial diets.

We developed a simple mass rearing technique using healthy booting stage rice plants. IR62 is used as a food plant because it is early maturing, high tillering, and YSB susceptible, but is resistant to several other insects and diseases that may infest a greenhouse culture.

The figure illustrates the YSB rearing procedure. Six hills of 14-d-old IR62 seedlings are transplanted weekly in a 34- × 25- × 11-cm plastic basin containing rice soil. At booting stage, about 63 d after sowing, tillers with bulging leaf sheaths are infested with 2 larvae/tiller. A 2.5-cm slit is cut along the midportion of the bulging leaf sheath. The incision is opened by spreading the cut edges to about 1 cm, which exposes a small section of the growing panicle. The slit is held open and YSB larvae are placed on the exposed panicle with a camel hair brush. When the edges of the slit close, the insects are trapped inside the boot. There should be no smoking during this procedure because newly hatched YSB larvae are highly sensitive to tobacco smoke.

Infested plants are placed in a 1.5- × 5.5- × 0.15-m water pan tray inside a large screen room. The water provides moisture for the plants and prevents ants from feeding on the insects. When the larvae have pupated at 25-30 d after infestation (DI) the plants are cut to 15-cm height and transferred to an adult emergence cage in another water pan tray. When adults emerge at 31-40 DI they are transferred to an oviposition cage containing 40- to 45-d-old potted TN1 plants. The YSB lay eggs on TN1 1-2 d after emergence.

Potted plants with egg masses are collected daily (32-41 DI) and placed in a water pan tray. To maintain the culture, the leaves of the TN1 plants with egg masses laid at 36 DI are cut into small pieces 4 d after oviposition. The leaf pieces are placed in test tubes or ball jars with moist cotton at the bottom. The eggs hatch at 42 DI. Larvae are then placed on booting plants and the cycle is repeated.

To provide larvae for experiments, cut leaves with egg masses at 32-35 DI and

Steps in rearing YSB for resistance studies. DI = d after infestation.

37-41 DI are placed in test tubes. The hatching larvae are for varietal screening for resistance or for basic studies of resistance mechanisms.

With these procedures, about 80% of all infested tillers produce an adult moth.

Each week at IRRI, we infest 10 plastic containers, each with 6 hills of 63-d-old plants, to maintain the insect culture and to infest 1 concrete bed (2.5 × 26 m) of about 1,500 30-d-old test plants for screening cultivars for resistance. □

Life cycle of *Marasmia patnalis*, a rice leaffolder in the Philippines

R. C. Joshi, E. Medina, and E. A. Heinrichs, IRRI

From Oct to Mar 1984, larvae of *M.*

patnalis Bradley (Lepidoptera:Pyralidae), identified by A. T. Barrion of IRRI, were observed folding and damaging rice leaves on the IRRI experiment farm. This leaffolder species is widely distributed in Southeast Asia. However, it has escaped the attention of rice entomologists

because the larva and adult, larval behavioral habits, and plant damage symptoms closely resemble those of the more commonly known leaffolder, *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*.

We studied the life cycle of *M. patnalis* in the greenhouse at 26-34°C and 70-80%